

Multivariate posterior inference for spatial models with the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation

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Abstract. The Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) is a convenient way to obtain approximations to the posterior marginals for parameters in Bayesian hierarchical models when the latent effects can be expressed as a Gaussian Markov Random Field (GMRF). In addition, its implementation in the **R-INLA** package for the R statistical software provides an easy way to fit models using INLA in practice in a fraction of the time than other computer intensive methods (e.g. Markov Chain Monte Carlo) take to fit the same model. Although INLA provides a fast approximation to the marginals of the model parameters, it is difficult to use it with models not implemented in **R-INLA**. It is also difficult to make multivariate posterior inference on the parameters of the model as INLA focuses on the posterior marginals and not the joint posterior distribution.

In this paper we describe how to use INLA within the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to fit complex spatial models and estimate the joint posterior distribution of a small number of parameters. We will illustrate the benefits of this new method with two examples.

In the first example, a spatial econometrics model with two autocorrelation parameters (for the response and the error term) is considered. This model is not currently available in **R-INLA**, and multivariate inference is often required to assess dependence between the two spatial autocorrelation parameters in the model. Furthermore, the estimation of spillover effects is based on the joint posterior distribution of a spatial autocorrelation parameter and a covariate coefficient.

In the second example, a multivariate spatial model for several diseases is proposed for disease mapping. This model includes a shared specific spatial effect as well as disease-specific spatial effects. Dependence on the shared spatial effect is modulated via disease-specific weights. By inspecting the joint posterior distribution of these weights it is possible to assess which diseases have a similar spatial pattern.

Keywords: Bayesian inference, Disease Mapping, INLA, MCMC, Spatial Econometrics

1. Introduction

Bayesian inference on complex hierarchical models have relied on Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC, henceforth) methods for many years. Inference with MCMC is based on drawing samples from the joint posterior distribution of the model parameters, which is often of a high dimension. For Bayesian hierarchical models with complex structure or large datasets, MCMC can be very computationally demanding. See, for example, Brooks et al. (2011) for a recent summary of MCMC methods.

To avoid dealing with high dimensional posterior distributions that are hard to estimate, Rue et al. (2009) focus on marginal inference and they develop a method to approximate the posterior marginal of the model parameters using the Laplace approximation and numerical integration. Also, they focus on models whose latent effects are a Gaussian Markov Random Field (GMRF, henceforth). GMRFs have several properties that can be exploited for computational efficiency when fitting Bayesian models (Rue and Held, 2005). This new method has been termed the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA, henceforth) and an implementation is available in the **R-INLA** package, that can cope with a large family of models.

Bivand et al. (2014) describe a novel approach to fit models not implemented in **R-INLA** with INLA. They note that some models can be fitted with **R-INLA** when one of the parameters is fixed, such as several models widely used in spatial econometrics (LeSage and Pace, 2009). In this particular case, the models can be fitted when the spatial autocorrelation parameter is fixed. As this parameter is in a bounded interval, values for the spatial autocorrelation parameters can be taken from a fine grid on its (bounded) support. Conditioning on these values, models can be fitted to obtain conditional posterior marginals of all the other parameters. The posterior marginal of the spatial autocorrelation parameter is then obtained by combining the marginal likelihoods of the fitted models and the prior using Bayes' rule. The posterior marginals for the remainder of the parameters in the model is obtained by averaging over the different conditional posterior marginals.

The former method can be easily extended to more than one parameter but as the number of parameter increases the number of models to be fitted increases exponentially. Also, it is problematic when the parameters that need to be fixed are not in a bounded

interval. Hence, if the model needs to be conditioned on several parameters to be fitted with **R-INLA**, a different approach is required.

Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018) suggest using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (Metropolis et al., 1953; Hastings, 1970) together with INLA when models need to be conditioned on several parameters. In this way, the joint posterior distribution of an ensemble of parameters can be obtained via MCMC, whilst the posterior marginals of all the other parameters is obtained by averaging over several conditional marginal distributions.

This paper is motivated by the need to fit complex spatial econometrics models and models for disease mapping with a weighted sum of several spatial effects, for which we are also interested in how to perform multivariate inference on a small ensemble of parameters. Multivariate inference on a small ensemble of parameters of the spatial models will rely on the output produced by the INLA within MCMC algorithm (Gómez-Rubio and Rue, 2018), i.e., samples from the joint posterior distribution of the ensemble of parameters.

This paper is structured as follows. A summary of INLA and a detailed description of the spatial models implemented in **R-INLA** is given in Section 2. Next, Section 3 covers how INLA can be used within the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to fit new spatial models. This is illustrated in Section 4, where two examples on spatial econometrics and joint disease mapping are developed. Finally, a summary and discussion is available in Section 5.

2. Spatial Models with the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation

The integrated nested Laplace approximation (Rue et al., 2009) provides a way to obtain approximations to the posterior marginals of effects and hyperparameters of a Bayesian hierarchical model that can be expressed as a latent Gaussian Markov random field (GMRF). Some recent developments are described in Martins et al. (2013); Rue et al. (2017), which will provide a good summary for those not familiar with INLA and the **R-INLA** package. More details can be found in Blangiardo and Cameletti (2015) (Chapter 4), where computational details are clearly explained and a full example for a Normal-Gamma model is developed.

In a latent GMRF, the means of observations $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$ are conveniently linked

to a linear predictor on latent effects \mathbf{x} , which have a multivariate Gaussian distribution with zero mean and variance covariate matrix that depends on a set of hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. INLA is able to provide accurate approximations to the posterior marginals of the latent effects $\pi(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{y}), i = 1, \dots, n_{\mathbf{x}}$ and hyperparameters $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}_j|\mathbf{y}), j = 1, \dots, n_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. These approximations will be denoted by $\tilde{\pi}(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{y})$ and $\tilde{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_j|\mathbf{y})$, respectively. Furthermore, INLA is also able to compute a number of other quantities of interest, such as different criteria for model assessment and choice. In particular, Rue et al. (2009) propose an approximation to the joint posterior of θ , $\tilde{\pi}(\theta|\mathbf{y})$. Note that this is often difficult to compute and that the approximation provided by INLA is very accurate (see, Hubin and Storvik, 2016; Gómez-Rubio and Rue, 2018, for details).

INLA is implemented as an R (R Core Team, 2018) package named **R-INLA**. In addition to providing a simple way of defining models and computing the approximation to the posterior marginals, **R-INLA** provides some extra features for model specification (see, Martins et al., 2013, for details) and can compute a number of derived quantities for model checking and model assessment. In particular, an approximation to the marginal likelihood of the model $\pi(\mathbf{y})$ is provided, which can also be used for model selection, for example.

Several authors (Gómez-Rubio et al., 2014; Bivand et al., 2015; Lindgren and Rue, 2015; Blangiardo and Cameletti, 2015) summarize the different spatial models available in **R-INLA** as latent effects that can be used to build models. We will provide a summary in this Section in order to provide an overview of what has already been implemented and what other spatial models have not been added yet. Furthermore, see Bakka et al. (2018) for a recent review on fitting spatial models with INLA.

Spatial latent effects for lattice data in **R-INLA** have a prior distribution which is a multivariate Normal distribution with zero mean and precision matrix τT , where τ is a precision parameter and T is a square and symmetric matrix. The structure of T will control how the spatial dependence is and it can take different forms to induce different types of spatial interaction. A description of the main spatial models implemented in INLA is available in the Supplementary Materials of this paper.

3. INLA within Markov Chain Monte Carlo

As described in the previous Section, **R-INLA** provides a large number of spatial latent effects that can be used to build more complex models. However, this list is far from exhaustive and it is difficult to implement new models in **R-INLA**. A possible approach to implement new models is the `rgeneric` latent effect that allows the user to define the latent model in R but this requires the user to specify the full structure of the latent effect as a GMRF. Furthermore, this generic approach will estimate the posterior marginal of the parameters in the latent effect, which are seldom adequate for multivariate posterior inference.

In order to extend the number of models that INLA can fit through the **R-INLA** package, Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018) propose the use of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (Metropolis et al., 1953; Hastings, 1970) together with INLA to fit some complex models not implemented in **R-INLA**. We will now introduce this new approach, that we will use to develop the examples in Section 4 to fit new spatial models and make multivariate inference using the joint posterior distribution of a small subset of parameters.

Let us denote by θ the ensemble of parameters and hyperparameters to be estimated in a Bayesian hierarchical models. Note that now θ will include some of the latent effects in \boldsymbol{x} and not only the hyperparameters θ described in Section 2. Similarly as Bivand et al. (2014), Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018) argue that very complex spatial models can be fitted with **R-INLA** when some of the parameters are fixed. Let us call these parameters θ_c so that θ becomes (θ_c, θ_{-c}) . By conditioning on θ_c , INLA can be used to obtain the posterior marginals of all the parameters in θ_{-c} , i.e., $\pi(\theta_{-c,i}|\boldsymbol{y}, \theta_c)$, and the conditional marginal likelihood $\pi(\boldsymbol{y}|\theta_c)$.

Li et al. (2012) deal with complex spatio-temporal models in a similar way by conditioning on some of the parameters at their maximum likelihood estimates. Although this is a reasonable way to proceed for highly parameterized models, it ignores the uncertainty of some of the parameters in the model when computing the posterior marginal of the other model parameters. Bivand et al. (2014) also fit spatial models conditioning on some of the model parameters at different values in a grid and then combine the resulting models to obtain the posterior marginals (not conditioned on θ_c) for the model of interest.

In order to estimate the posterior distribution of all the parameters in the model, the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm could be used to draw values for θ_c so that its joint posterior distribution can be obtained. At step $i+1$ of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm, new values $\theta_c^{(i+1)}$ for θ_c are proposed, but not necessarily accepted, from a proposal distribution $q(\cdot|\theta_c^{(i)})$. The new values are accepted with probability

$$\alpha = \min\left\{1, \frac{\pi(\mathbf{y}|\theta_c^{(i+1)})\pi(\theta_c^{(i+1)})q(\theta_c^{(i)}|\theta_c^{(i+1)})}{\pi(\mathbf{y}|\theta_c^{(i)})\pi(\theta_c^{(i)})q(\theta_c^{(i+1)}|\theta_c^{(i)})}\right\} \quad (1)$$

If the proposed value is not accepted, then $\theta_c^{(i+1)}$ is set to $\theta_c^{(i)}$.

Note that $\pi(\mathbf{y}|\theta_c^{(i+1)})$ is the marginal likelihood of the model conditioned on $\theta_c^{(i+1)}$, which can be obtained by fitting the model after fixing the values of θ_c to $\theta_c^{(i+1)}$. Also, this will provide the posterior marginals $\pi(\theta_{-c,i}|\mathbf{y}, \theta_c^{(i+1)})$ for all the parameters in θ_{-c} .

After a suitable number of iterations, the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm will produce samples from $\pi(\theta_c|\mathbf{y})$, from which the posterior marginals of the parameters in θ_c can be derived. Also, we will obtain a family of conditional marginal distributions for all the parameters in θ_{-c} . Their posterior marginals can be obtained by combining all these marginals as follows:

$$\pi(\theta_{-c,i}|\mathbf{y}) = \int \pi(\theta_{-c,i}|\mathbf{y}, \theta_c)\pi(\theta_c|\mathbf{y})d\theta_c \simeq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \pi(\theta_{-c,i}|\mathbf{y}, \theta_c^{(j)}) \quad (2)$$

Values $\{\theta_c^{(j)}\}_{j=1}^N$ represent N samples from $\pi(\theta_c|\mathbf{y})$ obtained with the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm.

Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018) state that the marginal likelihood used in Equation (1) is, in fact, an approximation. However, they argue that this error is very small because this approximation is very accurate (see, Hubin and Storvik, 2016, for a thorough study) and that the stationary distribution is very close to the actual posterior distribution. They also provide numerical evidence in a simulation study that supports that the using INLA within MCMC will provide an accurate approximation to the posterior distribution. In addition, Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018) illustrate the use of INLA within the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm with three examples, including fitting a simple spatial econometrics model. In addition to fitting models with unimplemented latent effects, this approach can be employed to use other priors not implemented in **R-INLA** (in

particular, multivariate priors) and to fit models with missing values in the covariates.

Finally, it is difficult to give a general rule for the choice of θ_c in highly parameterized models. As a simple rule, it can be taken such as the conditional model on θ_c is a latent Gaussian model and can be fitted with **R-INLA**. Similarly, θ_c can be chosen so that, when fixed, the resulting model is a Generalized Linear Mixed Model. In this case, the design matrix on the covariates will not depend on any other hyperparameters and the variance matrix of the random effects can be expressed as a precision parameter times a matrix with known structure (that does not depend on any other hyperparameters).

In the examples in the next Section we consider some spatial models and provide some hints on how to choose θ_c . Furthermore, we stress the importance of using INLA within MCMC for multivariate inference on any number of model parameters, a point that is not sufficiently addressed in Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018).

3.1. Alternatives to INLA within MCMC

INLA within MCMC can be regarded as a way to integrate out most of the parameters in the model so that we only need to deal with the set of parameters θ_c . In this way, INLA within MCMC uses MCMC to estimate the posterior distribution of θ_c , and the marginal distributions of the remainder of the parameters in the model are obtained by Bayesian model averaging. For this reason, INLA can be regarded as a device to reduce the dimension of the model to focus on a small subset of parameters θ_c .

INLA within MCMC can deal with any model that can be expressed as a conditional latent GMRF model. However, it is still a sequential algorithm that may take some time to converge. For this reason, we believe that other alternatives to estimate the posterior distribution of θ_c should be considered in practice.

First of all, instead of estimating the posterior distribution of θ_c these parameters may be fixed at their maximum likelihood estimates or posterior modes (if known) θ_c^m . This will simplify inference on θ_c (i.e., the posterior is a Dirac distribution at θ_c^m) and ignore the uncertainty about these parameters in the model but this approximation to $\pi(\theta_c|\mathbf{y})$ is simple to compute and it may also provide good approximations to the posterior marginals of the other parameters in the model. For example, Li et al. (2012) use a similar solution (e.g., fixing the values of some parameters in the model) to fit

spatio-temporal models for disease mapping.

Alternatively, the posterior distribution of θ_c may be estimated at a set of points at or close to the posterior mode. In particular, a central composite design (CCD, Box and Draper, 2007) can be used to place some points in the parametric space at which the posterior distribution of θ_c is computed. For any given point in the CCD design θ_c^* , its posterior density will be proportional to $\tilde{\pi}(\mathbf{y}|\theta_c^*)\pi(\theta_c^*)$, and these values can be rescaled to approximate the posterior density of θ_c^* and to obtain the weights used in Bayesian model averaging when computing the posterior marginals for all the other parameters in the model. This is similar to the approach used in INLA within MCMC but with the conditional models evaluated at a fewer number of points.

CCD is already implemented in **R-INLA** to estimate the posterior distribution of the hyperparameters, as described in Rue et al. (2017), for the latent models available therein. In our current proposal we are dealing with models not implemented in **R-INLA** or that are not latent GMRF (but conditional latent GMRF). CCD is used in a similar way as in **R-INLA** to set points in the parametric space of θ_c at which evaluate a conditional model. Note also that in this setting it is possible to fit all the conditional models in parallel and that this will take a fraction of the time required by INLA within MCMC. In order to obtain the points in the CCD design the **rsm** package (Lenth, 2009) will be used. Other authors that have used CCD designs to integrate some of the model hyperparameters out include Vanhatalo et al. (2013).

4. Examples

In this Section we provide two examples on how to fit complex spatial models with INLA using the **R-INLA** package and the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. Both models have a complex spatial structure, with several spatial terms, and they cannot be fitted with **R-INLA** alone. In addition, to fitting the model, we show how to exploit the joint posterior distribution obtained on a reduced ensemble of parameters to make multivariate inference. We will compare these results to those obtained by setting θ_c at some reasonable values (maximum likelihood estimate or posterior mode) or using CCD to estimate the posterior distribution of θ_c , as discussed in Section 3.1.

As stated in Section 3, the **rgeneric** latent effect in the **R-INLA** software could be

used to implement these models using the R language. However, this will only allow us to fit the models but not to provide multivariate posterior distributions on ensembles of the model parameters, which is also our aim in these examples.

4.1. Spatial Econometrics

Manski (1993) proposed the following general model for spatial econometrics that accounts for different levels of spatial dependence and interaction:

$$y = \rho W y + X\beta + W X\gamma + u; u = \lambda W u + e \quad (3)$$

y is the response variable made of observations in n areas, W an adjacency matrix, X a matrix of p covariates, $W X$ a matrix of lagged covariates, β and γ associated coefficients, and ρ and λ are spatial autocorrelation parameters. e is a multivariate Gaussian error term with zero mean and diagonal variance-covariance matrix $\sigma^2 I$, where I is the identity matrix of appropriate dimension.

This model has two autocorrelation terms, one on the response y and another one on the error term u , that are controlled by autocorrelation parameters ρ and λ , respectively. Spatial adjacency matrix W is often taken as a binary matrix, so that entry at row i and column j will be 1 if areas i and j are neighbors. Although this is a reasonable adjacency matrix, we will take W to be row-standardized, so that the sum of all the elements in a row add up to 1. This will bring interesting properties to the spatial autocorrelation parameters. In particular, they will be bounded in the interval $(1/\lambda_{min}, 1)$, where λ_{min} is the minimum eigenvalue of W (Haining, 2003).

LeSage and Pace (2009) fit this model using Bayesian inference, for which they assign priors to all model parameters. In particular, they consider typical independent inverse Gamma priors for all the precisions, vague independent Normal distributions for β and γ and uniform prior distribution for ρ and λ in the interval $(1/\lambda_{min}, 1)$.

In order to assess whether Manski's model can be fitted using standard software for linear regression, it can be rewritten as follows:

$$y = (I - \rho W)^{-1}(X\beta + W X\gamma) + u; u \sim MVN(0, \Sigma) \quad (4)$$

Here, the error term has a multivariate normal distribution with zero mean and variance-covariance matrix $\Sigma = \sigma^2[(I - \rho W')(I - \lambda W')(I - \lambda W)(I - \rho W)]^{-1}$.

Hence, this model has a non-linear term on ρ , $(I - \rho W)^{-1}$, that multiplies the linear predictor on the covariates and lagged covariates, and a complex error structure. This model cannot be fitted with **R-INLA** unless we condition on ρ and λ .

In order to fit this model with **R-INLA**, we have resorted to INLA with MCMC with $\theta_c = (\rho, \lambda)$. At each step of the algorithm we will obtain a conditional (on θ_c) posterior marginal for the remainder of the parameters in the model θ_{-c} . These conditional marginals will be later combined to obtain the posterior marginals of the model parameters θ_{-c} .

The proposal distribution for θ_c is the product of two Normal distribution centered at the current value of the parameters and standard deviation 0.25. This value has been obtained after some tuning to ensure a suitable acceptance rate. The starting point is $\theta_c = (0, 0)$. Then, 500 iterations were used as burn-in, followed by 5000 iterations more, of which one in 5 was kept to reduce autocorrelation. This provided a final 1000 samples to estimate the joint posterior distribution of θ_c . Note that thinning also involves the conditional distributions computed at each step of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm.

We have fit this model to the Columbus dataset (Anselin, 1988) which is available in **R** package **spdep**. This dataset contains information about 49 neighborhoods in Columbus (Ohio) in 1980. We will reproduce a classical analysis consisting on explaining crime rate on housing value (variable HOVAL) and household income (variable INC). We have not include lagged covariates, so that $\gamma = 0$.

In addition to using INLA within MCMC, we have also fitted this model using Gibbs sampling using the **rjags** package (Plummer, 2016) and using maximum likelihood with function `sacsarlm()` from the **spdep** package (Bivand and Piras, 2015).

Both MCMC and INLA within MCMC have to deal with the computation of matrices $(I - \lambda W)$ and $(I - \rho W)$ are their determinants. This is a an important topic in spatial econometrics and several approximations have been proposed (see LeSage and Pace, 2009; Bivand et al., 2013, and the references therein). As an alternative, we use a CCD design (as described in Section 3.1), which is centered at the maximum likelihood estimates and inscribed in the box defined by taking ± 0.75 standard errors (as reported

by function `sacsar1m`) from the maximum likelihood estimates. Note that INLA within MCMC averages over 1000 posterior marginals whilst INLA with CCD will only use 10 posterior marginals. Also, with a CCD design matrices $(I - \lambda W)$ and $(I - \rho W)$ and their determinants only need to be computed at handful of points, which will reduce computational burden.

Finally, we have also considered the approximation based on setting the values of ρ and λ at their maximum likelihood estimates (which will be denoted as INLA at ML). In the current example, these values can be obtained very fast and fitting a model with INLA conditional on these values provides marginals for all the other parameters in the model. Although these posterior marginals ignore the uncertainty about ρ and λ , they can be regarded as approximations to their respective posterior marginals in the Manski model.

Figure 1 shows the posterior marginal distributions of the autocorrelation parameters, estimated using INLA within MCMC, INLA with CCD, MCMC and maximum likelihood. As it can be seen, there is good agreement between the different estimates. Regarding the other parameters in the model, Figure 2 summarizes the different estimates and how they seem to agree. Note that these marginals have been obtained in different ways. For INLA within MCMC, they are obtained by averaging the conditional marginals obtained at each step of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. With INLA with CCD, they have been averaged over the marginals obtained from the models fitted at the 10 CCD points. Finally, for INLA at ML, the marginals are those fitted by INLA after fixing ρ and λ at their maximum likelihood estimates.

The non-MCMC methods seem to provide narrower posterior marginals for the intercept and variance, but this probably due to the fact that they do not account for all the variability associated to the spatial autocorrelation parameters. However, these methods are computationally faster than MCMC and INLA within MCMC, and still provide reasonable approximations to the posterior marginals of these parameters.

Finally, the joint posterior distribution of (ρ, λ) is shown in Figure 3. The bivariate distributions obtained with INLA within MCMC and MCMC look alike. The maximum likelihood estimate has also been added to the plots (as a black dot), and in both plots looks close to the mode of the joint posterior distribution. Although no estimate of the

Figure 1. Estimates of the spatial autocorrelation parameters of the Manski model using INLA within MCMC, INLA with CCD, MCMC and maximum likelihood. Vertical lines represent values obtained with maximum likelihood estimation.

Figure 2. Estimates of the intercept, covariate coefficients and variance using INLA within MCMC, INLA with CCD, MCMC and INLA with ρ and λ fixed at their maximum likelihood estimates (INLA with ML). Covariates are housing value (HOVAL) and household income (INC). Vertical lines represent values obtained with maximum likelihood estimation.

Figure 3. Joint posterior distribution of (ρ, λ) . The solid dot represents the maximum likelihood estimate.

joint posterior distribution is provided for INLA with CCD, posterior summary statistics could be computed and these can be plugged in to a bivariate Gaussian distribution to approximate $\pi(\rho, \lambda | \mathbf{y})$.

4.1.1. Computation of the impacts

Spill over effects, or how changes in the covariates in one area affect the response at its neighbors, are of interest in spatial econometrics. These measures are often called *impacts* and they are defined using partial derivatives as

$$\frac{\partial y_i}{\partial x_{jr}} \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n; \quad r = 1, \dots, p \quad (5)$$

Each covariate will have an associated matrix of impacts which, for the model that we are considering, is:

$$S_r(W) = [I - \rho W]^{-1}(\beta_r + W\gamma_r), \quad r = 1, \dots, p \quad (6)$$

Note that each element in that matrix will measure how a change in covariate r in area j will impact on the response in area i . These are often summarized as the average *direct*, *indirect* and *total* impacts.

Direct impacts measure changes in the response in the same area where the change occurs, indirect impacts measure changes in adjacent areas and total impacts are the sum of direct and indirect impacts. For this reason the average direct impact is defined

as the mean of the trace of the impacts matrix, the average indirect impact is the sum of all the off-diagonal impacts divided by n and the total impact is the sum of all the elements in the impacts matrix divided by n .

Following the details in LeSage and Pace (2009) and Gómez-Rubio et al. (2017), the average total impact for the Manski model for a covariate r is

$$\frac{1}{1 - \rho} \beta_r, \quad (7)$$

and the average direct impact is

$$n^{-1} \text{tr}((I - \rho W)^{-1}) \beta_r + n^{-1} \text{tr}((I - \rho W)^{-1} W) \gamma_r. \quad (8)$$

Here, $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ denotes the trace of a matrix. Average indirect impacts can be obtained by taking the difference between total and direct impacts.

As discussed in Gómez-Rubio et al. (2017), computing the impacts requires multivariate inference as the distribution depends on the (joint) posterior distribution of ρ , β_r and γ_r . Hence, computing the impacts from the posterior marginals of these parameters alone is not enough to obtain accurate estimates. Note that in our particular case we are not considering lagged covariates and that $\gamma_r = 0$, which simplifies the computation of the impacts.

To compute the impacts we can exploit the fact that we have different models conditioned on the values of ρ . Hence, we could compute the marginal distribution of the impacts for each value of ρ obtained with the Metropolis-Hastings and the conditional (on ρ) marginal $\pi(\beta_r | \mathbf{y}, \rho)$. Then we could average over all conditional marginal distributions of the impacts given ρ to obtain the final distribution of the impacts, which could be used to compute summary statistics.

Table 1 summarizes point estimates and standard deviations of the different average impacts considered in this example. The estimation methods for which the impacts are reported are MCMC, INLA within MCMC, INLA with CCD, INLA at ML and maximum likelihood estimates obtained with the functions in the **spdep** package. In general, all Bayesian methods provide very similar results, with INLA-based approaches reporting slightly smaller standard deviations than MCMC.

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation (in parenthesis) of the impacts for the Manski model without lagged covariates fitted to the Columbus dataset. Covariates are housing value (HOVAL) and household income (INC).

Method	INC			HOVAL		
	Direct	Indirect	Total	Direct	Indirect	Total
MCMC	-0.96 (0.37)	-0.46 (0.42)	-1.42 (0.66)	-0.30 (0.10)	-0.14 (0.14)	- 0.44 (0.20)
INLA w/ MCMC	-0.97 (0.33)	-0.44 (0.35)	-1.40 (0.48)	-0.30 (0.10)	-0.13 (0.10)	-0.43 (0.14)
INLA w/ CCD	-1.06 (0.40)	-0.54 (0.29)	-1.60 (0.49)	-0.29 (0.12)	-0.15 (0.09)	-0.44 (0.15)
INLA at ML	-1.06 (0.32)	-0.53 (0.36)	-1.59 (0.48)	-0.29 (0.10)	-0.14 (0.11)	-0.43 (0.14)
Max. lik.	-1.10 (-)	-0.55 (-)	-1.65 (-)	-0.29 (-)	-0.15 (-)	-0.44 (-)

4.2. Joint Modeling of Three Diseases

Spatial models have been used for a long time in disease mapping to study the spatial variation of disease. Several authors have used INLA to fit spatial and spatio-temporal models for disease mapping of a single disease as MCMC methods are often very slow when the number of areas is large. See Blangiardo and Cameletti (2015) for a recent summary. Modeling several diseases is more complex because it requires models with a multivariate response and it often involves non-linear terms on some parameters in the linear predictor of the model (Leroux et al., 1999; Bivand et al., 2015). Knorr-Held and Best (2001) have considered the joint modeling of two diseases by including a shared spatial effect (with different weights for each disease) plus specific spatial terms for each disease.

In the next example we extend this model to create a multivariate model for three diseases following Downing et al. (2008). They fit a joint model to six diseases with different weighted shared and specific spatial components. In our case, we will only consider three diseases, which are modeled using a shared spatial term and specific spatial patterns.

In particular, let us assume that we have a study region divided into n smaller areas and that we are interested in modeling D diseases. Observed counts of disease d in area i will be denoted by $O_i^{(d)}$. Similarly, $E_i^{(d)}$ will represent the expected cases of disease d in area i . The model that we will be fitting is

$$O_i^{(d)} \sim Po(E_i^{(d)}\theta_i^{(d)}) \tag{9}$$

Here, $\theta_i^{(d)}$ is the relative risk for disease d in area i , which is modeled as

$$\log(\theta_i^{(d)}) = \alpha^{(d)} + v_i \cdot \delta^{(d)} + s_i^{(d)}; \quad i = 1, \dots, n; \quad d = 1, \dots, D \quad (10)$$

Parameter $\alpha^{(d)}$ is a disease-specific intercept and it sets the baseline of the log-relative risks for disease d , v_i is a shared component to all diseases, $\delta^{(d)}$ is a parameter that controls how the shared component affects disease d and $s_i^{(d)}$ are specific components to each disease. The shared and specific components can include different types of fixed and random effects. Knorr-Held and Best (2001) use a partition model to split areas into regions of similar risk, but other effects can be considered (see, for example, Thomas et al., 2004).

Note that this model looks like a standard log-linear model and that, for a fixed value of $\delta^{(d)}$, it could be fitted with some standard software packages for Bayesian inference, including **R-INLA**. We will use our new approach to fit this model by taking $\theta_c = \boldsymbol{\delta} = (\delta^{(1)}, \dots, \delta^{(D)})$. In **R-INLA**, this value can be included as a weight of the effects in the linear predictor using a latent effect of type `besag`.

The prior for $\delta^{(d)}$ will be a log-Normal distribution with mean 0 and a precision equal to 0.1 to provide vague prior information. Shared component v_i will be an intrinsic CAR spatial effect with precision τ_v . Specific components will also have an intrinsic CAR spatial effect with precision τ_s (which can be easily modeled using the `replicate` feature in **R-INLA**).

We will fit this model to the cases of lip, oral cavity and pharynx tumors (ICD-10 C00-C14), esophagus tumor (ICD-10 C15) and stomach tumor (ICD-10 C16) from 1996 to 2014 at the province level in mainland Spain. Expected cases were computed using age-sex standardized rates from period 1996 - 2014.

Standardized Mortality Ratios (i.e., $O_i^{(d)}/E_i^{(d)}$) for each disease are shown in the maps in Figure 4. Stomach tumors seems to have a spatial pattern that is different, and the other two diseases seem to have a very similar spatial pattern. We expect that the model described earlier would capture this joint spatial pattern and account for the different overall rates by means of the disease specific intercepts included in the specific components.

Similarly as in the previous example, we will study how other approximations will work. In this case, maximum likelihood estimates of $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ are not easy to obtain and we will

Figure 4. Standardized Mortality Ratio of lip, oral cavity and pharynx cancers, esophagus cancer and stomach cancer in Spain in the period 1996-2014.

rely on the posterior means and standard deviations to create the CCD design. Given that the hyperparameters are positive in this model, the CCD design will be considered in the log-scale. It will be centered at the log-posterior modes reported by MCMC and within 0.75 times the posterior standard deviations in the log-scale. The standard deviations can be obtained from the MCMC output or approximated using the Delta method (see Hosmer et al., 2008, Appendix 1) from the posterior means and variances of δ . In this case, they will be $(\sigma^{(d)}/\mu^{(d)})^2$, where $\mu^{(d)}$ is the posterior mean and $\sigma^{(d)}$ the posterior standard deviation of $\delta^{(d)}$.

Note that in this case it is not easy to find values to create the CCD design as in the previous example. In any case, our aim with this comparison is to investigate how other faster approximations will work. In addition, the CCD design now produces a set of 16 different values for the spatial weights and it seems to be concentrated about the posterior modes. Furthermore, another approximation based on fitting the model at the posterior mode of δ will be used. This will be denoted by INLA at MODE.

Figure 5 summarizes the estimates obtained with MCMC (Gibbs sampling with WinBUGS), INLA within MCMC, INLA with CCD and INLA at MODE. The top row shows the estimates of the posterior distribution of weights $\delta^{(d)}$ for the three diseases for which there is a very good agreement between both estimation methods. INLA with CCD performs reasonably well considering that it is based on 16 models and the CCD design seems to be too concentrated about the posterior modes. INLA at MODE simply shows a vertical line at the posterior mode of $\delta^{(d)}$.

An interesting question now is how spatial dependence between the three causes

Figure 5. Summary of the posterior marginals of $\delta^{(d)}$ (top line) and summary of bivariate posterior distributions of $(\delta^{(i)}, \delta^{(j)})$, $i \neq j$, obtained with INLA within MCMC (center line) and MCMC (bottom line).

of death could be assessed. Figure 5 also shows the bivariate posterior distributions of each pair of spatial weights. These plots show the strong correlation between the weights associated to oral cavity and esophagus cancers, and how the weight associated to stomach cancer seems to be independent from the two other weights. This supports the idea that stomach cancer has a distinct spatial pattern and that oral cavity and

esophagus cancers have a similar spatial pattern. Furthermore, there is a very good agreement between the estimates obtained with INLA within MCMC and MCMC.

It is also worth mentioning that INLA with CCD can also provide approximations to the posterior correlations between the spatial weights by dividing the posterior estimate of the covariance by the posterior estimates of the standard deviations. For $\delta^{(1)}$ and $\delta^{(2)}$ this value 0.41, whilst for $\delta^{(3)}$ and any of the other two weights it is 0.12. The same correlations computed from the MCMC output are higher but this is due to the fact that the CCD design is concentrated about the posterior mode of $\boldsymbol{\delta}$. In any case, the positive dependence between the first two diseases is also captured by the INLA with CCD approximation. Note that it is not possible to explore the dependence between the different diseases with the model fitted using INLA at MODE.

Finally, Figure 6 displays the marginal distributions of the disease specific intercepts $\alpha^{(d)}$ and precisions that appear in the model. For INLA within MCMC, these have been obtained by doing an average of the conditional marginals obtained at each step of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. In general, there is good agreement between this approach and MCMC. Regarding INLA with CCD and INLA at MODE, they provide good estimates of the disease-specific intercepts and the precision of the disease-specific random effects. However, they seem to not account for all the variability in the estimation of the precision of the shared spatial random effect, as the posterior marginal is centered at the posterior mode but with a smaller variance.

Although it is not shown here, we have observed a positive strong correlation between $\delta^{(1)}$ and $\delta^{(2)}$. We believe that this happens because of the similar spatial pattern that both diseases have. $\delta^{(3)}$ shows less correlation with the other two weighing parameters. This kind of multivariate inference has also been possible because we have been able to estimate the joint posterior distribution of $(\delta^{(1)}, \delta^{(2)}, \delta^{(3)})$ by fitting the model with INLA within MCMC.

5. Discussion

Gómez-Rubio and Rue (2018) develop a novel approach to fit Bayesian models not implemented in the **R-INLA** by combining Metropolis-Hastings and INLA. In this paper we have exploited this method to show how to fit complex spatial models with several spatial

Figure 6. Marginal distributions of the parameters in the model obtained by Bayesian model averaging the conditional marginals obtained at each step of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. Solid lines represent estimates obtained with INLA within MCMC and the dashed line represents the marginals obtained with MCMC.

components so that multivariate inference on a small ensemble of important parameters is feasible as their joint posterior distribution is obtained. This joint posterior distribution can also be used to compute the posterior distribution of any function on these ensemble of parameters. Furthermore, we have also explored how simpler approximations will work when fitting complex spatial models, which provide good approximations to most of the posterior marginals of the parameters at a reduced computational cost. These simpler approaches are based on estimating the posterior distribution of the hyperparameters using a CCD design or simply by fixing their values at the maximum likelihood estimates or posterior modes.

As seen in the examples presented in this paper, INLA within Metropolis can be used to fit complex spatial models with a simple implementation of the Metropolis-

Hastings algorithm. This implementation is simpler compared to a full implementation of the model using several MCMC algorithms as sampling only involves a few parameters. Furthermore, convergence of the MCMC simulations is achieved in less iterations because the number of parameters that need to be simulated from is greatly reduced compared to fitting the model completely using MCMC. For large datasets, this should be an interesting alternative as INLA can fit conditional models faster than MCMC.

The choice of the set of hyperparameters θ_c to condition on can be chosen in different ways. In general, any choice that makes the conditional model a latent GMRF that can be fitted with INLA will work. In many applications it will be enough to choose θ_c so that the conditional model is a Generalized Linear Mixed Model that can be easily fitted with INLA. This is how we have selected the hyperparameters in θ_c in the examples developed in this paper. In most cases, the dimension of θ_c will be small, but INLA within MCMC can be applied to sets of hyperparameters of any dimension.

For cases in which the spatial model can be fitted completely with **R-INLA**, the approach presented in this paper is also appealing because it makes multivariate inference based on the joint posterior possible. Although we have focused on spatial models, the methods presented in this paper can be easily applied to any other model that can be expressed as a conditional GMRF and, hence, can be fitted with **R-INLA** by conditioning on a small number of parameters.

In the future we hope to explore alternatives to the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm that can fit the required conditional models in parallel. In particular, importance sampling can be a good alternative as sampling of values of θ_c can be performed in parallel. Furthermore, INLA within MCMC can be embedded into reversible jump MCMC algorithms in order to tackle the problem of model fitting and model selection at the same time. This could be useful, for example, to perform variable selection in complex spatial or spatio-temporal models.

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